

Effect of lignin-rich *Vitex negundo* leaf extract on antioxidant, thrombolytic, antiproliferative, antidepressant, and cytotoxic activities in mice

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Abstract: In several countries, *Vitex negundo* have been claimed to have anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antioxidant activities. It's frequently used in folk medicine for the treatment of various pain disorders. The methanol extract of *Vitex negundo* leaves was studied for its biological effects. To investigate different biological exertions of the methanol extract of *Vitex negundo*, the leaf extracts were obtained with pure methanol. *In-vitro* anti-oxidant activity was resolved using a DPPH radical scavenging assay. A clot lysis test was used to assess the thrombolytic activity. Antiproliferative effects of DMSO *Vitex negundo* in cell lines acquired from human cervix adenocarcinoma (HeLa cells). Using the brine shrimp lethality bioassay method, the plant extracts were evaluated for cytotoxic action. LC₅₀ values were determined through probit analysis of mortality percentages. In hole cross-test and open-field test, neuropharmacological activities of mice were assessed in mice. The findings revealed that *Vitex negundo* leaf extract possessed antioxidant effects, streptokinase exposed significant clot lysis and human cervix adenocarcinoma cells demonstrated mild cervical antiproliferative activity. Significant neuropharmacological action (antidepressant and anxiolytic) and cytotoxic action were shown by the methanol extract of *Vitex negundo* leaves.

Introduction

Several biological activities of natural phytochemicals, such as antioxidant, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory qualities, have been documented [1, 2]. From the ancient era to till, people have frequently used natural remedies for every disease while they are facing old or new health problems or other illnesses [3]. A tiny tree or shrub called *Vitex negundo* is used in traditional Chinese medicine to treat a wide range of ailments [4]. The presence of lignins, saponins, phenols, glycosides, alkaloids, sterols, and tannins in *Vitex negundo* leaves extracts (VNLE) is responsible for its diverse biological activities [5]. *Vitex negundo* displays numerous types of pharmacological properties due to lignans, iridoid glycosides, and terpenoids which demonstrated antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer activities [6]. *Vitex negundin*, *vitexilactone*, *vitetrolin D*, *artemetin*, *vitexicarpin*, and *penduletin* chemicals are among the labdane-type

diterpenoids found in *V. negundo* leaves (VNL). These compounds can suppress the growth of malignant cell lines, specifically K562 Lu1, KB, and LNCaP [7]. Nevertheless, how cytotoxic labdane-type diterpenoids are against liver and breast malignancies has not yet been explained [8]. Leaves have antihistamine, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory qualities. Leprosy, dyspepsia, rheumatism, and piles are all treated with roots [9]. The flowers are used for cholera. Fruits are used as an anthelmintic [10]. The entire plant is used as a diuretic, antiseptic, antipyretic, and for inflammations [11, 12]. With the potential medicinal application, the objective of the current study is to observe the phytochemical constituents of VNL, as well as its antioxidant, thrombolytic, anticancer, cytotoxic, and antidepressant properties to offer a solid scientific backing for useful clinical use and traditional utilization.

Materials and methods

Plant collection: The plant sample was collected from Chittagong District, Bangladesh during April and May 2023. It was authenticated at the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Science and Technology Chittagong with a voucher specimen no. PUSTC: 0223. VNL was properly cleaned to remove any remaining sand or dust. The 10.0 kg leaves were obtained by carefully separating the bough. After that, for two weeks, the leaves were dried in the absence of direct sunlight; through shade drying. The leaves were ground to get powder via a grinder. The resultant fine powder was 800 g stored in an airtight container and kept cool, dry, and dark until used.

Preparation of methanol extract: 800 g of VNL powder and 2.0 L of methanol were kept in two cleaned beakers. The bottles were kept tightly closed for 14 days with occasional shaking. By this time, a major portion of the powder had dissolved in methanol, which was further filtered by using cotton wool [13]. The residual methanol was removed by a rotary evaporator at 45°C and reduced pressure. The 176 g of methanol extract that resulted was stored in a refrigerator until used. The percentage yield of methanol extract was calculated [14-16].

Qualitative phytochemical screening

Test for flavonoids: A few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added to a small amount of VNLE. Flavonoids are detected by the immediate development of red colour [17].

Test for saponins: The crude extract and 5.0 mL of distilled water were combined in a test tube and shaken firmly. It is believed that the production of steady foam indicated the presence of saponin [18].

Test for tannins: Test with ferric chloride, 5.0-10.0 mL of filtered water was mixed with 0.5 g of leaf extract, and then 5.0% ferric chloride solution were added. The green precipitate is a sign that tannins exist [19].

Test for steroid: In Salkowski's test, 1.0 ml of chloroform was combined with 2.0 mg of the extract, and a few drops of H₂SO₄ that was concentrated were included presence of steroids was identified by a red hue formed in the bottom chloroform layer.

Liebermann-Burchard's test: After dissolving 2.0 mg of dry extract in acetic anhydride, heating the mixture to boiling, cooling it down, and then adding 1.0 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ along the test tube's sides. Steroid presence was identified by the production of a green hue.

Test for glycosides: Salkowski's evaluation, 2.0 mL chloroform was combined with the crude extract. After that, 2.0 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added and gently shaken. The glycone part of the glycoside, or steroidal ring, was visible as a reddish-brown tint.

Test for anthraquinones glycosides: 1.0 g VNL powder was added to a test tube, followed by the addition of 20 mL chloroform. For 5.0 min, it was heated in a steam bath. Filter the extract while it's still warm and let it cool

afterwards. The filtrate was mixed with an equal volume of 10.0% ammonia solution. When the test tube was shaken, the top layer of bright pink coloration became visible, signifying the manifestation of anthraquinones. 10.0 mL of 10.0% ammonia and 5.0 mL chloroform were added to the test tube for control tests [20].

Test for reducing sugar: In Fehling's test, 2.0 mg of dry extract was dissolved in 1.0 mL of distilled water before adding Fehling's (A+B) solution. The test is validated by the formation of a brick-red precipitate [21].

Benedict's test: A test tube containing 5.0 mL of Benedict's reagent and 0.5 mL of the extract was heated in a water bath for 5.0 to 10.0 min. The solution's colour changes from green, yellow, or red to indicate the presence of the reducing sugar depending on the reducing sugar amount present in the test solution [22].

Antioxidant activity: The 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay was used to perform the VNL extract *in vitro* [23]. Thus, 10.0 mg of extract was dissolved in 10.0 mL of methanol, yielding a stock solution with 1000 µg/mL. Three solutions of 1000, 500, and 250 µg/mL were obtained by serial dilutions from this. DPPH was prepared without a sample using the sample preparation method, and ascorbic acid (1000, 500, and 250 µg/mL) was used as a standard. 0.004%w/v DPPH solution was made by dissolving 4.0 mg of DPPH in 100 mL of methanol and was kept at 20°C. Following a thorough shake and 30 min at room temperature in the dark, 2.0 mL of extract or standard in various concentrations was added to 3.0 mL of DPPH solution. The absorbance of the studied samples was measured using a UV-vis spectrophotometer with methanol serving as a blank [24, 25].

Thrombolytic activity: Streptokinase (SK) with 15,000,000,000 I. U. was used, and 5.0 mL of sterile distilled water was added and thoroughly mixed to perform thrombolysis *in-vitro*, suspension's stock was made of 100 µl (30,000 I. U.) [26].

Human specimen: 20 healthy human volunteers who had never used oral contraceptives or anticoagulant medication before provided the 4.0 mL whole blood sample. The three weighed microcentrifuge tubes were used to transfer 0.5 mL of blood to form clots.

Herbal preparation: 10.0 mL of distilled water was mixed with 100 mg of VNLE using a vortex mixer. The soluble supernatant was extracted from the suspension after it had been drained overnight and passed through a syringe filter with a pore size of 0.22 microns. By adding 100 µl of the herb's aqueous preparation to the microcentrifuge tubes, the clot samples were examined for thrombolytic activity [27].

Experimental methods: Venous blood sample was extracted from healthy individuals and placed into separate, sterile, pre-weighed Alpine tubes (500 µl). After that, the tubes were incubated at 37°C for 45 min. Following clot formation, serum was expelled (aspirated out without disturbing the formed clot). Every tube that held a clot was weighed once more to determine the clot's weight. The clot weight was determined by weighing each tube containing a clot once more. A correct marking of 100 µl of plant extract was added to each Alpine tube containing a clot. Each tube was kept at 37°C for 90 min while the clot lysis was observed the use of SK and water was for positive and negative (no thrombolytic) controls.

Anticancer activity: HeLa is a human cervical cancer cell line that is maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM), which contains 1.0% penicillin-streptomycin, 0.2% gentamycin, and 10.0% foetal bovine serum. Following a 24-hour incubation period at 37°C with 5.0% CO₂, cells were seeded at 2.0x10⁵ 100 ml onto a 96-well plate. Two days later, each well received a 50 µl sample. Each well received a 50 µl sample the next day. An inverted light microscope was used to examine cytotoxicity after 48 hrs of incubation. Methanol extracts of VNL were put to the test against HeLa cell lines [28].

Brine shrimp cytotoxicity activity: To perform the cytotoxicity analysis on brine shrimp nauplii, the Meyer method was utilized. The lethality bioassay for brine shrimp was conducted using DMSO as a negative control (cytotoxic test). An aquarium store in Chittagong, Bangladesh was the source of the dried cyst of brine shrimp.

The development of mature shrimp known as nauplii from dried brine shrimp cysts was made possible by the use of synthetic seawater, specifically an artificial seawater solution consisting of 3.8% NaCl, and vigorous aeration. Vincristine sulphate (2.0 mg/vial) served as a positive control. The serial concentration was then ascertained by dilution at 125, 250, 500, and 1000 µg/mL. Using a magnifying glass, the number of nauplii brine shrimp that survived each vial was counted after 24 hours period [29, 30].

Neuropharmacological screening

Testing groups: Utilizing the hole cross-test and open-field test, the neuropharmacological properties of the VNLE were assessed. Four groups of five mice in each group were used in each experiment: **Group 1:** Control: 0.5 mL per mouse, 1.0% Tween 80, **Group 2:** Positive control: 1.0 mg/kg of diazepam, **Group 3:** Test-1: VNL-200 mg/kg, and **Group 4:** Test-2: VNL-400 mg/kg.

Hole-cross test: A wooden box measuring 30cmx20cmx14cm was used to conduct the hole-cross test. A partitioning wall with a hole diameter of 3.0cm was used to construct a hole-cross apparatus, which was positioned 7.5cm above the floor. After giving each mouse an oral dose of the test agent, they were promptly placed on one side of the designated device. The mice were seen to move freely through the hole and between chambers for three minutes. At 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 min, the inspection was conducted [31].

Open field test: There were three mice in all groups, which were split up into test, positive, and control groups. The test group was provided 200 and 400 mg/kg of VNLE orally, incidentally, the control group was given 1.0% Tween. 1.0 mg/kg diazepam was administered to the positive control group. The equipment stood 40cm tall, and the open-field floor was covered in squares that alternated between black and white. After the mice were given the oral intake, the number of squares they explored was recorded for three minutes at 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 min [32].

Ethical approval: This study was approved by the University of Sciences and Technology Chittagong. Based on the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Animal Research, the committee has approved the protocol number: USTC/AEAC/23/024.

Statistical analysis: One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate the data among the groups, reporting the results with mean±SEM. Tukey's multitudinous assessment tests were used to find significant differences between the means of the groups at $p < 0.05$ using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25.0.

Results

Percentage yield and phytochemical profile of VNLE: The bioactive profile of the methanol extract of VNL is displayed in **Table 1**. The bioactive percentage yield of the VNL methanol extract was 22.0%.

Table 1: VNLE bioactive constituent's observation

Secondary metabolite	Name of the test	Observation	Findings
Flavonoids	Hydrochloric acid test	Orange to red to crimson	++
Saponins	Foam test	Stable foam	++
Tannins	Ferric chloride test	Greenish black precipitate	++
Steroid	Salkowski's test	The lower layer of chloroform is red	++
	Liebermann Burchard's test	The green color at the junction	++
Anthraquinones glycosides	Test for free anthraquinone	Red color	++
Glycosides	Salkowski's test	Orange-reddish color	++
	Benedict's test	Brick red precipitate	++
Reducing Sugar	Fehling's test	Precipitation that is brick red or red	++

(+) = Presence of phytochemical

Antioxidant test (DPPH scavenging): The antioxidant capacity of VNLE, determined via the DPPH assay, was contrasted with ascorbic acid, an established antioxidant. The extract elicited a negligibly significant level of DPPH scavenging activity in tests with $IC_{50} = 691.423 \mu\text{g/mL}$ contrasted to standard ascorbic acid ($536.75 \mu\text{g/mL}$). In both of these tests, the extract showed dose-dependent activity. **Figure 1** illustrates the DPPH scavenging activity of VNL methanol extract and ascorbic acid respectively.

Figure 1: The DPPH-scavenging properties of ascorbic acid and VNL methanol extract

In-vitro thrombolytic activity: **Figure 2** displays the *in-vitro* thrombolytic activity results and their means. Thus, 10 mg/mL of VNL triggered clot lysis with a 59.5% efficiency after treatment with 100 µl, whereas, 100 µl of SK (30,000 IU) caused 68.3% of the clots to lysis compared to the negative control (10.9%) clot lysis.

Figure 2: *In-vitro* thrombolytic activity of VNL methanol extract and Streptokinase

In-vitro antiproliferative activity: The VNLE on HeLa cell viability was decreased to 70-80 concentration of reduction in HeLa cells was observed at 50 µg/mL (**Table 2**). The HeLa cells gradually separated post-VNLE treatment. The change in morphology of HeLa cells is depicted in **Figure 3**.

Table 2: *In vitro* antiproliferative effect by observing the cell viability against HeLa cells

Group	Cell viability
Control (solvent)	100%
DMSO (2.5%) & Solvent	>95%
VNLE (50 µg/mL)	70-80%

Figure 3: *In vitro* anticancer activity of VNLE and DMSO on human cervical carcinoma cell line

Brine shrimp cytotoxicity activity: 293.494 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ is the LC_{50} value for vincristine sulfate determined by equation (Table 3). When vincristine sulphate was present at 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, the death rate was pragmatically 80.0% at 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, on the other hand, 35.0% of deaths were found. Using the equation, the LC_{50} value (100.53 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) is obtained and presented by VNLE along with the fatality percentage. Figure 4 shows that at 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of VNLE, the mortality rates were 100% and 65.0%, respectively.

Table 3: The regression values of brine shrimp cytotoxic effect

Group	Regression value
Vincristine sulphate	$y = 1.39x + 1.57$
VNLE	$y = 2.588x - 0.182$

Figure 4: *In-vivo* cytotoxic activity of VNL methanol extract and vincristine sulphate

Statistical significance differences among numerous therapeutics are indicated by different alphabets

Neuropharmacological activity

Hole-cross test: The number of holes visited by the mice in the healthy control group did not change between 0 and 60 minutes (Figure 5). The 0-minute to 90-minute movement of the hole cross-test in VNLE-treated groups decreased compared to the initial value. A dose of 400 mg/kg exhibited a maximum suppression of locomotor activity which is similar to diazepam ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 5: *Vitex negundo* methanolic extract's effect on exploratory behaviour

Statistical significance among numerous therapeutics is indicated by different alphabets

Open-field test: During the open-field test, the VNL-treated groups (200 and 400 mg/kg), demonstrated a noteworthy and dose-dependent decline in movement between 0 minutes and 120 minutes at the baseline, as demonstrated in **Figure 6**. At the 400 mg/kg dose level, the number of squares the mice travelled decreased significantly from its initial value at 0 minutes to 90 minutes ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 6: Effect of VNLE on mice's investigational behaviour in an open-field test

Variations in alphabets denote statistical significance among various treatments

Discussion

Plants naturally contain substances called phytochemicals that have a range of therapeutic uses [33, 34]. The diverse phytochemicals present in plants, including alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, phenols, steroids, and carotenoids, all contribute to their protective benefits against inflammation, diabetes, aging, microbes, parasites, depression, cancer, oxidative damage, and wound healing [31, 35]. Flavonoids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, steroids, anthraquinone glycosides, glycosides, and reducing sugars were found in VNL's methanol extracts. The capacity to donate hydrogen is what gives DPPH, a free radical with a reputation for being highly

stable, its antioxidant effect on DPPH radical scavenging [36]. This assay is typically used to assess the phenolic components in plant extracts' antioxidant qualities [21]. In this assay, the prevalence of antioxidant components in plant extract is indicated by the change of DPPH solution to DPPH, which is yellow [37]. The antioxidant activity of VNLE assay using the DPPH method. The higher the percentage of the inhibitory effect, the greater the antioxidant capacity of the extracts. Conversely, the bigger the antioxidant activity of the extracts, the smaller the IC_{50} value. The scavenging effect of the reference standard ascorbic acid was 97.0% at the highest concentration whereas the IC_{50} value was much less (536.75 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) which showed its highly effective potential as a free radical scavenger. The negative control methanol also showed no antioxidant activity. VNLE showed a dose-dependent free radical scavenging effect compared to that of the reference.

Thrombolysis involves dissolving dangerous blood clots to maintain blood flow and protect tissues and organs from damage. An internal haemorrhage occurring due to blood accumulation poses a risk to vital organs. SK is a thrombolytic agent that dissolves blood clots. A thrombolytic mediator catalyses the formation of plasmin from plasminogen, which then liquefies blood clots. This proteolytic enzyme can prevent fibrin particles from cross-linking [38]. Herbs, leaves, fruits, and seeds are encompassed by sources that have fibrinolytic, anti-clotting, and anti-platelet characteristics. At 10 mg/mL, VNL's clot lysis capacity was significantly higher than that of the negative control (10.9%), with a value of 59.5%, which was significant compared with the negative control while the capability for clot lysis for SK was 68.3%. The VNLE contains flavonoids responsible for its thrombolytic properties. Hela cells were exposed to VNLE for cytotoxicity assessment. Hela cells' propagation and viability were decreased by the VNLE concentration range. Vinblastine, irinotecan, topotecan, and paclitaxel, derived from plants, have proven clinical efficacy as anticancer drugs. Flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and polyphenols undergo various biological interactions with enzymes and toxic proteins, resulting in cellular toxicity or growth inhibition [38]. Studies suggest that flavonoids found in natural plants are responsible for their cytotoxic and anticancer effects, significantly contributing to chemoprevention via influence on cell signalling and angiogenesis. Flavonoids, a type of polyphenolic compound, play a significant role in cancer prevention [40, 41]. Previous studies reported high levels of polyphenols in VNLE. Because of its chemotherapeutic qualities, VNLE may have killed Hela cells [42].

Brine shrimp lethality (BSL) assay is uncomplicated, as it does not necessitate aseptic conditions, completes within 24 hours, is cost-effective, and does not require any specialized equipment. BSL assay is an *in-vivo* monitor for discovering, screening, and monitoring bioactivities (cell-line toxicity, antitumor, cytotoxic, phototoxic, pesticidal, trypanocidal, enzyme inhibition, and ion regulation) within natural compounds. Cytotoxic properties in the BSL assay were determined as follows: safe within the range of and nontoxic in the range $LC_{50} > 1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$; weak within the range $500 \geq LC_{50} \leq 1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$; moderate within the range $100 \geq LC_{50} \leq 500 \mu\text{g/mL}$; and strong within the range $0.0 > LC_{50} < 100 \mu\text{g/mL}$. The crude methanol, petroleum ether, and carbon tetrachloride fractions, obtained from the VNL, were shown to have cytotoxic activity. The cytotoxic activity of agnuside and negundoside from VNL was demonstrated using a BDL assay. The bark of *V. negundo* verified significant cytotoxic activity against brine shrimp larvae [43]. The VNLE and vincristine sulphate caused brine shrimp larvae to die in a dose-dependent manner in our study. Higher cytotoxicity was observed in the case of VNLE [LC_{50} of 100.53 $\mu\text{g/mL}$] than that of vincristine sulphate [LC_{50} of 293.49 $\mu\text{g/mL}$]. The VNLE, rich in phenolics and flavonoids, may account for the high shrimp mortality rate due to its anti-tumor properties [44]. The hole-cross test and open-field test are the typically used experiments for assessing an animal's exploratory tendencies [45, 46]. Diazepam is known to reduce animal exploration and locomotor activity in response to a new environment [47]. CNS depressant drugs, like diazepam, negatively impact animal performance on the hole cross-test and open-field test due to anxiolytic activity, decreased ambulatory activity, and sedation [46, 47]. At 200 and 400 mg/kg doses, VNLE significantly declined the number of animal holes crossed and the number of squares visited. Simultaneously, a dose of 1.0 mg/kg of

diazepam also resulted in a comparable pattern of effects to that seen with VNLE across all experiments [48]. However, to recapitulate, more insightful scientific research is required to generate further reproducible outcomes in the sectors of antioxidant, thrombolytic, antiproliferative, neuropharmacological, and cytotoxic activities. Still, apart from these, some other activities must be evaluated so that the potentiality of the seeds of this medicinal plant can be assessed appropriately. The limitation of this study is that was performed mostly *in-vitro*. There are substantial differences in *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* test results. Additionally, crude methanol extract was utilized rather than the isolation of bioactive compounds available in that extract. Generally, the crude extract contains a mixture of different types of compounds. Therefore, it is possible that one compound's bioactivity can be antagonized by other compounds available. Hence, compound isolation and molecular docking approaches can allow us to know the real potential.

Conclusion: It is plausible that the methanol extract of *Vitex negundo* leaves like diazepam, reacts with the central nervous system, as evidenced by the animals' reduced motor coordination, anxiolytic exertion, and sedation.

References

1. Azad AK, Wan Azizi WS, Adham SA, Yee BL (2016) Maggot debridement therapy for diabetic foot ulcer: Experience from Maggot Treatment Centres. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2 (1): 23-25. doi: Nil.
2. Azad AK, Sulaiman WMAW (2020) Antidiabetic effects of *P. macrocarpa* ethanolic fruit extract in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 6 (1): 57. doi: 10.1186/s43094-020-00073-7
3. Azad AK, Babar ZM, Wan Mohd Azizi WS, Sunzida NK (2016) The significance of *murrayakoenigii* (L.) spreng leaves: A mini-review. *PharmacologyOnLine*. 2: 18-25. doi: Nil.
4. Neha B, Jannavi R, Sukumaran P (2021) Phyto-pharmacological and biological aspects of *Vitex negundo* medicinal plant-a review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*. 33 (29A): 17-32. doi: 10.9734/jpri/2021/v33i29A31562
5. Vo GV, Nguyen THT, Nguyen TP, Do THT, Tran NMA, Nguyen HT, Nguyen TT (2022) In silico and *in vitro* studies on the anti-cancer activity of artemetin, vitexicarpin and penduletin compounds from *Vitex negundo*. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*. 30 (9): 1301-1314. doi: 10.1016/j.jsps.2022.06.018
6. Kamal N, Mio Asni NS, Rozlan INA, Mohd Azmi MAH, Mazlan NW, Mediani A, Baharum SN, Latip J, Assaw S, Edrada-Ebel RA (2022) Traditional medicinal uses, phytochemistry, biological properties, and health applications of *Vitex* sp. *Plants (Basel)*. 11 (15): 1944. doi: 10.3390/plants11151944
7. Sharma RL, Prabhakar A, Dhar KL, Sachar A (2009) A new iridoid glycoside from *Vitex negundo* Linn (Verbenaceae). *Natural Products Research*. 23 (13): 1201-1209. doi: 10.1080/14786410802696494
8. Xin H, Kong Y, Wang Y, Zhou Y, Zhu Y, Li D, Tan W (2013) Lignans extracted from *Vitex negundo* possess cytotoxic activity by G2/M phase cell cycle arrest and apoptosis induction. *Phytomedicine*. 20 (7): 640-647. doi: 10.1016/j.phymed.2013.02.002
9. Raama Murthy J, Venkataraman S, Meera R, Desmukh KS, Chidambaranathan N, Devi P (2010) Phytochemical investigation and antipyretic activity of leaf extract of *Vitex negundo* Linn. *International Journal of PharmTech Research*. 2 (2): 1068-1073. Corpus ID: 88727670.
10. Tiwari OP, Tripathi YB (2007) Antioxidant properties of different fractions of *Vitex negundo* Linn. *Food Chemistry*. 100 (3): 1170-1176. doi: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2005.10.069
11. Sichaem J, Nguyen HH, Nguyen VH, Mac DH, Mai DT, Nguyen HC, Duong TH (2021) A new labdane-type diterpenoid from the leaves of *Vitex negundo* L. *Natural Products Research*. 35 (14): 2329-2334. doi: 10.1080/14786419.2019.1672687
12. Dechayont B, Phuaklee P, Chunthong-Orn J, Juckmeta T, Prajuabjinda O, Jirratsatit K (2021) Antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of Mahanintangtong and its constituent herbs, a formula used in Thai traditional medicine for treating pharyngitis. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*. 21 (1): 105. doi: 10.1186/s12906-021-03274-6
13. Lakshmanashetty RH, Nagaraj VB, Hiremath MG, Kumar V (2010) *In vitro* antioxidant activity of *Vitex negundo* leaf extracts. *Chiang Mai Journal of Sciences*. 37 (3): 489-497. doi: Nil.

14. Khan MZ, Azad AK, Jan S, Safdar M, Bibi S, Majid AMSA, Abdel-Daim MM (2023) An experimental and computational analysis of plant compounds from whole *Urtica dioica* L. plant's essential oil for antioxidant and antibacterial activities. *Metabolites*. 13 (4): 502. doi: 10.3390/metabo13040502
15. Gul H, Naseer RD, Abbas I, Khan EA, Rehman HU, Nawaz A, Abdel-Daim MM (2022) The therapeutic application of *Tamarix aphylla* extract loaded nanoemulsion cream for acid-burn wound healing and skin regeneration. *Medicina*. 59 (1): 34. doi: 10.3390/medicina59010034
16. Azad AK, Awang M, Rahman MM, Akter SFU (2012) Biological and pre-clinical trial evaluation of a local medicinal plant *bacopa monnieri* (L.) Penn. *International Journal of Current Research and Review*. 4 (19): 92-99. Corpus ID: 73337419.
17. Das BK, Al-Amin MM, Russel SM, Kabir S, Bhattacharjee R, Hannan JMA (2014) Phytochemical screening and evaluation of analgesic activity of *Oroxylum indicum*. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 76 (6): 571-575. PMID: PMC4293694.
18. Rai S, Kafle A, Devkota HP, Bhattarai A (2023) Characterization of saponins from the leaves and stem bark of *Jatropha curcas* L. for surface-active properties. *Heliyon*. 9 (5): e15807. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon. 2023.e15807
19. Abdelfatah AM, Fawzy M, El-Khouly ME, Eltaweil AS (2021) Efficient adsorptive removal of tetracycline from aqueous solution using phytosynthesized nano-zero valent iron. *Journal of Saudi Chemical Society*. 25 (12): 101365. doi: 10.1016/j.jscs.2021.101365
20. Baliyan S, Mukherjee R, Priyadarshini A, Vibhuti A, Gupta A, Pandey RP, Chang CM (2022) Determination of antioxidants by DPPH radical scavenging activity and quantitative phytochemical analysis of *ficus religiosa*. *Molecules*. 27 (4): 1326. doi: 10.3390/molecules27041326
21. Shaikh JR, Patil M (2020) Qualitative tests for preliminary phytochemical screening: An overview. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*. 8 (2): 603-608. doi: 10.22271/chemi.2020.v8.i2i.8834
22. Singh V, Kumar R (2017) Study of phytochemical analysis and antioxidant activity of *Allium sativum* of Bundelkhand region. *International Journal of Life Sciences Research*. 3 (6): 1451-1458. doi: 10.21276/ijlssr. 2017.3.6.4
23. Azad AK, Laboni FR, Rashid H, Ferdous S, Rashid SS, Kamal N, Labu ZK, Islam Sarker Z (2020) *In vitro* evaluation of *Cuscuta reflexa* Roxb. for thrombolytic, antioxidant, membrane stabilizing and antimicrobial activities. *Natural Product Research*. 34 (16): 2394-2397. doi: 10.1080/14786419.2018.1538216
24. Azarbani F, Hadi F, Jafari S, Murthy HA, Azad AK (2023) Antimicrobial, antifungal and antiradical activities of the essential oils from the flower and leaf extracts of Iranian *Ferulago macrocarpa* plant. *Journal of Herbal Medicine*. 39: 100658. doi: 10.1016/j.hermed.2023.100658
25. Wang F, Tan J, Jiang R, Li F, Zheng R, Yu L, Zheng Y (2023) DPPH radical scavenging activity of new phenolics from the fermentation Broth of Mushroom *Morehella importuna*. *Molecules*. 28 (12). doi: 10.3390/molecules28124760
26. Nahar N, Fatema UK, Sharma PP, Bhuiya AM, Begum T, Azahar NF, Rahman MNA, Sulaiman WMABW, Azad AK (2024) Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, anthelmintic, and thrombolytic activity of the methanol extract of *Citrullus Lanatus* peel. *Universal Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 9 (2): 7-14. doi: 10.22270/ujpr.v9i2.1085
27. Babu V, Devi CS (2015) *In vitro* thrombolytic activity of purified streptokinase extracted from *Streptococcus equinus* VIT_VB2 isolated from bovine milk. *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis*. 39 (1): 71-78. doi: 10.1007/s11239-014-1093-2
28. Azad AK (2016) Phytochemical and toxicity evaluation of *Phaleria macrocarpa* (Scheff.) Boerl by MCF-7 cell line and brine shrimp lethality bioassay. *Journal of Coastal Life of Medicine*. 4 (1): 45-49. doi: 10.12980/JCLM. 4.2016J5-194
29. Azad AK, Azizi WS, Ismail AFH, Abbas SA, Uddin J, Labu ZK (2019) Phytochemical and toxicity evaluation of traditional herb: *Lagerstroemia speciosa* L. (Banaba) by MCF-7 cell line and brine shrimp lethality bioassay. *Bangladesh Pharmaceutical Journal*. 22 (1): 45-49. doi: 10.3329/bpj.v22i1.40072
30. Azad AK, Islam MA, Sunzida NK (2019) Cytotoxicity study of *Basella alba* leaves extract on brine shrimp lethality bioassay and MTT assay. *PharmacologyOnLine*. 8 (2): 87-93. Corpus ID: 233766815.
31. Diniz TC, de Oliveira Júnior RG, Miranda Bezerra Medeiros MA, Gama e Silva M, de Andrade Teles RB, dos Passos Menezes P, da Silva Almeida JRG (2019) Anticonvulsant, sedative, anxiolytic and antidepressant activities of the essential oil of *Annona vepretorum* in mice: Involvement of GABAergic and serotonergic systems. *Biomedicine and Pharmacotherapy*. 111: 074-1087. doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2018.12.114
32. Jimenez JA, McCoy ES, Lee DF, Zylka MJ (2024) The open field assay is influenced by room temperature and by drugs that affect core body temperature. *F1000Res*. 12: 234. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.130474.4
33. Mendoza N, Silva EME (2018) Introduction to phytochemicals: Secondary metabolites from plants with active principles for pharmacological importance. In: *Phytochemicals-source of antioxidants and role in disease prevention*. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.78226

34. Akhlaq M, Khaleeq Alum M, Mehboob Alam M (2022) Anti-inflammatory potential of medicinal plants. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2 (1): 13-21. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6399381
35. Sami A, Usama M, Saeed MM, Akram M (2021) Medicinal plants with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory-like activity. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 1 (3): 25-32. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5534605
36. Radojevic ID, Stankovic M, Stefanovic O, Topuzovic M, Čomić L (2012) Antioxidative and antimicrobial properties of different extracts from *Sideritis Montana L.* *Romanian Biotechnological Letters*. 17 (2): 7160-7168. doi: Nil.
37. Muflihah YM, Gollavelli G, Ling Y-C (2021) Correlation study of antioxidant activity with phenolic and flavonoid compounds in 12 Indonesian indigenous herbs. *Antioxidants*. 10 (10): 1530. doi: 10.3390/antiox10101530
38. Mohamad T, Kanaan E, Ogieuhi IJ, Mannaparambil AS, Ray R, Al-Nazer LWM, Ahmed HM, Hussain M, Kumar N, Kumari K, Nadeem M, Kumari S, Varrassi G (2024) Thrombolysis vs anticoagulation: Unveiling the trade-offs in massive pulmonary embolism. *Cureus*. 16 (1): e52675. doi: 10.7759/cureus.52675
39. Gahtori R, Tripathi AH, Kumari A, Negi N, Paliwal A, Tripathi P, Upadhyay SK (2023) Anticancer plant-derivatives: deciphering their oncopreventive and therapeutic potential in molecular terms. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 9 (1): 1-20. doi: 10.1186/s43094-023-00465-5
40. Amawi H, Ashby CR, Samuel T, Peraman R, Tiwari AK (2017) Polyphenolic nutrients in cancer chemoprevention and metastasis: Role of the epithelial-to-mesenchymal (EMT) pathway. *Nutrients*. 9: 911. doi: 10.3390/nu9080911
41. Birt DF, Hendrich S, Wang W (2001) Dietary agents in cancer prevention: Flavonoids and isoflavonoids. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*. 90 (2-3): 157-177. doi: 10.1016/S0163-7258(01)00137-1
42. Badgajar NV, Mistry KN, Chudasama PN, Patel JS (2017) *In vitro* antioxidant and cytotoxic effects of methanol extracts of *Vitex negundo*, *lantana camara*, *bauhinia variegata* and *bauhinia racemosa* on human cancer cell lines. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 79 (3): 431-437. doi: 10.4172/pharmaceutical-sciences.1000246
43. Clemen-Pascual LM, Macahig RAS, Rojas NRL (2022) Comparative toxicity, phytochemistry, and use of 53 Philippine medicinal plants. *Toxicology Reports*. 9: 22-35. doi: 10.1016/j.toxrep.2021.12.002
44. Zheng CJ, Zhao XX, Ai HW, Lin B, Han T, Jiang YP, Qin LP (2014) Therapeutic effects of standardized *Vitex negundo* seeds extract on complete Freund's adjuvant induced arthritis in rats. *Phytomedicine*. 21 (6): 838-846. doi: 10.1016/j.phymed.2014.02.003
45. Seibenhener ML, Wooten MC (2015) Use of the open field maze to measure locomotor and anxiety-like behavior in mice. *Journal of Visualized Experiments*. 96: 52434. doi: 10.3791/52434
46. Bazine HA, Shlaka MA, Sherif FM (2023) A neuropharmacological profile of *lyceum schweinfurthii* (solanaceae) methanolic extract in mice. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 3 (1): 43-50. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771364
47. Alwasia AN, Altawirghi NM, Sherif FM (2018) Pharmacological evaluation of the Libyan folk herb *Retama Raetam* seeds in mice. *International Journal of Academic Health and Medical Research*. 2 (11): 1-6. doi: Nil.
48. Rico JL, Muñoz-Tabares LF, Lamprea MR, Hurtado-Parrado C (2019) Diazepam reduces escape and increases closed-arms exploration in gerbils after 5 min in the elevated plus-maze. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 10 (4): 748. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00748
49. Widyastiwi W, Roseno M (2022) Anxiolytic activity of ethanolic extract of three species of Indonesian Lempuyang (*Zingiber zerumbet*, *Zingiber aromaticum*, and *Zingiber americans*). *Open Access Macedonian Journal Med Sciences*. 10 (A): 695-701. doi: 10.3889/oamjms.2022.9132

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